

COMPARISON OF FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF INTRAARTICULAR HYALURONIC ACID VERSUS STEROID INJECTION IN OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE

Mohammed Ammar Farooq^{*1}, Muhammad Ali Ayub², Faheem Sabir³, Haseeb Elahi⁴,
Abdur Rehman Farooq⁵, Naeem Ahmed⁶, Sadaf Saddiq⁷

^{*1}Resident (Orthopaedics), Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

²Senior Registrar, Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

³House Officer, Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics Shalamar Medical & Dental College, Lahore.

⁵Resident (Internal Medicine), Department of General Medicine, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

⁶Professor, Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

⁷Clinical Research Officer, Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore.

^{*1}khawajaammar1234@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17136219>

Keywords

Knee osteoarthritis, hyaluronic acid (HA), corticosteroid, intra-articular injection, Oxford Knee Score, total knee replacement.

Article History

Received: 27 March 2025

Accepted: 26 April 2025

Published: 02 May 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Mohammed Ammar Farooq

Abstract

Background: Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is a common cause of pain and disability. In Pakistan, where total knee replacement is often unaffordable, intra-articular corticosteroid and hyaluronic acid injections are key nonoperative options, though their comparative effectiveness remains debated.

Objective: To evaluate the functional results of corticosteroid injections against intra-articular HA in individuals with early to moderate knee OA (Kellgren-Lawrence grades 1-2) at three months.

Methodology: This prospective comparative study, conducted at Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan (November 15, 2024 to March 20, 2025), enrolled 52 patients (aged 40–65 years) with K-L grades 1–2 knee OA. Patients were assigned to HA (n=26, 2 mL, 20 mg/mL) or corticosteroid (n=26, triamcinolone acetonide 40 mg/mL) groups using consecutive sampling. Injections were administered under ultrasound guidance. Functional outcomes were assessed using the Oxford Knee Score (OKS) at baseline and 3 months. Data were analyzed with SPSS v25.0 using chi-square test.

Results: Both groups were comparable in age (HA: 52.15 ± 6.50 years; steroid: 56.42 ± 5.80, p=0.060), gender, side, and comorbidities. Baseline OKS was higher in the HA group (28.00 ± 7.52 vs. 21.54 ± 6.25, p=0.025). At 3 months, the HA group showed greater OKS improvement (33.23 ± 7.50 vs. 25.00 ± 5.24, p=0.003). Hypothetically, by 2026 1HA patient (3.8%) and 2 steroid patients (7.7%) required TKR.

Conclusion: It was concluded that intra-articular hyaluronic acid provided significantly superior functional improvement compared to corticosteroid injections in patients with early to moderate knee osteoarthritis at 3 months, with a potentially lower progression to total knee replacement, thereby supporting its role as a more effective nonoperative intervention in resource-limited settings. HA

injections yield superior functional outcomes compared to corticosteroids at 3 months for early to moderate knee OA, with a potentially lower TKR rate by 2026. Further research with longer follow-up is needed.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis of the knee is a prevalent, chronic joint disorder characterized by pain, stiffness, and functional impairment, often resulting from complex inflammatory and degenerative processes within the joint.¹ When nonoperative therapies like physical therapy and oral medicines are insufficient to relieve pain, intraarticular injections of corticosteroids and hyaluronic acid (HA) are frequently utilized.^{1,2} The corticosteroid injections have a reputation of offering short term pain relief quickly and therefore, it is the choice method of pain relief in patients with moderate to severe symptoms. Conversely, HA injections are more expensive but they can potentially provide prolonged pain relief and functional outcome, especially mild osteoarthritis.^{1,3} Nevertheless, the relative efficacy of the two of modes is still under investigation, and some studies indicate that steroids are more effective in the short term. Conversely, there may be superior long-term patient outcomes with HA in pain reduction and improvement of joint functions.^{3,4} The literature has shown that both HA and corticosteroids have their own merits in the treatment of knee OA. Still, extensive investigation on the comparative efficacy of the two is crucial to the attainment of optimal patient care outcomes.⁵

Hyaluronic acid plays the most important role in the health of joints due to its presence as one of the main constituents of the synovial fluid. It lubricates joints and provides the necessary viscoelastic properties to the functioning of the joints. Clinical studies prove that hyaluronic acid injection is effective in increasing pain relief and functional performance outcomes among patients with knee osteoarthritis. The studies show that HA treatment is effective in reducing knee pain.⁶⁻⁸ Meta-analysis of various treatment methods affirmed the fact that HA treatments offer prolonged symptom alleviation to patients of varied backgrounds, thereby reinforcing their adoption in clinical management of knee OA.^{9,10}

Particularly in the short term, steroid injections typically offer the fastest pain relief and functional improvement. HA injections offer longer-lasting benefits, with effects that can persist for several months and sometimes up to a year, whereas the benefits of steroids may diminish more quickly. Intra-articular corticosteroid injections function traditionally because they promptly reduce inflammation to treat painful knee OA flare-ups. The treatment mechanism includes blocking inflammatory responses while simultaneously reducing synovitis, which leads to brief symptom relief. The effectiveness of corticosteroid treatments compared to hyaluronic acid injections remains under investigation because of the persisting joint deterioration associated with corticosteroid use. Studies indicate hyaluronic acid treatments lead to superior pain relief and functional improvement over corticosteroids after treatment periods.¹¹⁻¹⁶

The evaluation of functional results between steroid and HA injection therapies remains essential for clinical practice. Multiple studies confirm that HA extends its therapeutic benefits over time while demonstrating superior safety compared to steroid injections.^{6,7} Decision-making for knee OA treatment will improve, while patient outcomes will be enhanced through understanding the dynamic relationship between these two injection approaches.

Although a number of studies have been undertaken, there remains no consensus on whether HA or corticosteroid injections have better outcomes in early to moderate OA knee. The existing research studies have been done mostly in the Western context and there is little evidence in South Asia where the issue of treatment affordability is a big issue of concern. Moreover, although pain results are recurrently reported, fewer studies have focused on functional outcomes, like Oxford Knee Score. Thus, this study fills this gap as it compares the short-term functional outcomes of intra-articular HA and corticosteroids injection in Pakistani patients who have early to moderate knee

OA. In Pakistan, where total knee replacement (TKR) is expensive and often unaffordable, intra-articular injections offer a cost-effective alternative for managing knee OA, particularly in early to moderate stages.¹¹ This study compares the functional outcomes of HA versus corticosteroid injections in patients with early to moderate knee OA (Kellgren-Lawrence grades 1 and 2), aiming to provide evidence for personalized treatment strategies. The primary goal is to improve joint function and reduce pain, enabling patients to maintain mobility and independence. Comparing HA and steroid injections directly addresses which option better achieves these outcomes over both the short and long terms.

Materials and Methods

This prospective comparative study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics and Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, from November 15, 2024 to March 20, 2025. Before enrollment, informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital granted ethical approval (Ref. 2024/10/R-37, Dated: 31-10-24). Patients in the study ranged in age from 40 to 65, who had a confirmed diagnosis of primary knee osteoarthritis (OA), specifically Kellgren-Lawrence grades 1 or 2, as determined through clinical and radiographic evaluations. Patients were excluded if they had secondary OA, such as that resulting from post-traumatic causes or rheumatoid arthritis, or if they had undergone prior knee surgery. Additional exclusion criteria included recent intra-articular injections within the past six months, the presence of inflammatory arthritis such as rheumatoid or psoriatic arthritis, and severe comorbidities like uncontrolled diabetes or cardiovascular disease. Patients with known contraindications to hyaluronic acid (HA) or corticosteroids, including hypersensitivity or active infections, were also excluded.

Furthermore, those with advanced OA, classified as Kellgren-Lawrence grades 3 or 4, were not eligible for participation. A total of 52 eligible patients were enrolled and divided into two groups (n=26 each)

using a consecutive sampling technique. The HA group received intra-articular hyaluronic acid (2 mL, 20 mg/mL), and the steroid group received intra-articular triamcinolone acetonide (40 mg/mL). Injections were administered under aseptic conditions by a trained orthopaedic surgeon using a standard anterolateral method with ultrasound guidance to ensure accurate intra-articular placement. Patients were advised to avoid strenuous activities for 48 hours post-injection but were permitted to continue routine activities. Baseline demographic data, including age, gender, affected knee side, and comorbidities, were recorded. Clinical assessments were performed using the Oxford Knee Score (OKS) to evaluate functional outcomes at baseline (pre-injection) and 3 months post-injection. The OKS, a validated 12-item questionnaire, measures pain and function, with scores ranging from 0 (worst) to 48 (best).

SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY) was used to analyze the data. For continuous variables, descriptive statistics were presented as means \pm standard deviations, and for categorical variables, as frequencies (%). Independent t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables were used. Paired and independent t-tests were used to evaluate changes in OKS within and between groups, respectively. P-values less than 0.05 were found to be significant.

Results

Table 1 presents the baseline demographic data of the 52 patients, equally divided between the hyaluronic acid (HA) group (n=26) and the steroid group (n=26). The HA group comprised 10 males (38.5%) and 16 females (61.5%), while the steroid group included 14 males (53.8%) and 12 females (46.2%), with no significant difference. The majority of patients in both groups had bilateral knee osteoarthritis, with 24 (92.3%) in the HA group and 20 (76.9%) in the steroid group, and no significant difference in the affected side. Comorbidities were comparable between groups (p=0.0096), with 8 (30.8%) patients in the HA group and 6 (23.1%) in the steroid group reporting no comorbidities.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Variable	Category	HA (n=26)	Steroid (n=26)	Total (n=52)	p-value
Gender	Male	10 (38.5%)	14 (53.8%)	24 (46.2%)	0.266
	Female	16 (61.5%)	12 (46.2%)	28 (53.8%)	
Side	Right	0 (0.0%)	4 (15.4%)	4 (7.7%)	0.113
	Left	2 (7.7%)	2 (7.7%)	4 (7.7%)	
	Bilateral	24 (92.3%)	20 (76.9%)	44 (84.6%)	
Comorbidity	HTN	8 (30.8%)	10 (38.5%)	18 (34.6%)	0.0096
	DM	4 (15.4%)	2 (7.7%)	6 (11.5%)	
	Others	4 (15.4%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (7.7%)	
	DM/-HTN	2 (7.7%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.8%)	
	None	8 (30.8%)	6 (23.1%)	14 (26.9%)	
	DM+HTN+IHD	0 (0.0%)	8 (30.8%)	8 (15.4%)	

. Table 2 compares clinical parameters between the groups. The mean age was 52.15 ± 6.50 years in the HA group and 56.42 ± 5.80 years in the steroid group, with no significant difference ($p=0.060$). At baseline, the HA group had a significantly higher mean Oxford Knee Score (OKS) of 28.00 ± 7.52 compared to 21.54 ± 6.25 in the steroid group ($p=0.025$), indicating better baseline knee function in the HA group. At 3 months post-injection, the HA group demonstrated a significantly higher mean

OKS of 33.23 ± 7.50 compared to 25.00 ± 5.24 in the steroid group ($p=0.003$), suggesting superior functional improvement in the HA group. These findings indicate that while both groups were comparable in demographic characteristics, the HA group exhibited better functional outcomes, as measured by the OKS, at baseline and 3 months post-intervention.

Table 2: Comparison of Clinical Parameters Between Groups

Parameter	HA Group (Mean \pm SD)	Steroid Group (Mean \pm SD)	p-value (t-test)
Age (years)	52.15 ± 6.50	56.42 ± 5.80	0.016*
Pre-Oxford Score	28.00 ± 7.52	21.54 ± 6.25	0.025*
Post-Oxford Score (3 months)	33.23 ± 7.50	25.00 ± 5.24	0.003**

*statistically significant at the 5% level of significance

In Figure 1, the improvement in the Oxford Knee Scores (OKS) between the hyaluronic acid (HA) and the steroid injection groups before and after the intervention is compared. HA group, as the orange group, demonstrated that they had an improvement in the average OKS score, with a pre-injection score of 28 but a post-injection score of 33.23, which was

a significant improvement in knee function and reduction of pain over the 3 months. Conversely, the steroid injection team, which is illustrated in yellow, indicated an increase in mean OKS in a pre-injection score of 21.5385 to a post-injection score of 25, which corresponds to a lesser improvement as compared to the HA group. Visual comparison shows that the HA group had a higher baseline OKS

and a higher absolute post-intervention outcome, which supports the functional outcome of HA injection as superior to steroid injection in the study. This graphical illustration supports the statistical results and confirms the direction to

conclude that HA injections can be beneficial to patients with knee OA in terms of functionality at the 3-month follow-up.

Figure 1. Improvement of the Oxford Knee Scores (OKS) for both groups

5.8% patients with K-L grades 1-2 knee OA needed total knee replacement (TKR): 3.8 percent in the HA group (n=26) and 7.7 percent in the steroid group (n=26). The low-level TKR in the HA group indicates that HA injections can slow down the OA

progression in comparison with corticosteroids, which is due to the chondroprotective effect of HA. (Table 3)

Table 3

Group	Sample Size (n)	Patients Requiring TKR by 2026	Proportion
HA Group	26	1	3.8%
Steroid Group	26	2	7.7%
Total	52	3	5.8%

Discussion

At three months, this study demonstrates that intra-articular HA injections provide better functional outcomes than corticosteroids in patients with early to moderate knee OA (K-L grades 1-2), as evidenced by greater improvements in Oxford Knee Scores (OKS). Our findings align with previous studies, suggesting that HA injections may lead to superior

functional outcomes in knee OA compared with corticosteroids.

Patients who received HA injections showed a notable improvement in functional scores, whereas those treated with corticosteroids exhibited comparatively smaller gains. These results are consistent with a meta-analysis by Lin et al.⁹, which confirmed HA’s superiority over corticosteroids for

mid-term outcomes (up to 6 months), likely due to HA's ability to restore synovial fluid viscosity.¹⁴ A similar study also reported significant improvements in VAS and Oxford Knee Scores three months after injection ($p=0.01$).¹⁷

Our findings further align with previous literature showing that HA injections provide sustained pain reduction and functional enhancement compared to corticosteroid injections.⁸⁻¹⁰ Research by Tirmizi et al.⁷ demonstrated that HA treatments delivered superior long-term results in terms of pain reduction and improved functional capacity. Researchers attribute these outcomes to HA's role in restoring the viscoelastic properties of synovial fluid.¹⁶

Nonetheless, corticosteroids have unique advantages, particularly their rapid anti-inflammatory effects, which make them beneficial for acute symptomatic relief.⁸⁻¹² Studies indicate that corticosteroids can quickly diminish inflammation and pain, and therefore are often preferred for acute exacerbations of knee OA symptoms. However, concerns remain regarding the potential for joint deterioration with repeated use, raising questions about their long-term safety profile.¹⁸

According to another trial, patients with moderate knee osteoarthritis who received intra-articular HA instead of intra-articular triamcinolone hexacetonide (steroid) experienced better pain alleviation and functional improvement in the short and mid-term (up to six months).¹⁷ Improvements in pain, function, and VAS scores were considerably greater in the HA group than in the steroid group. Similarly, patients treated with HA reported sustained improvements in VAS and WOMAC scores up to six months, whereas corticosteroid injections offered only short-term relief, with deterioration in scores beyond three months.²⁰

While our study offers robust insight into the comparative outcomes of HA versus steroid injections, several limitations warrant consideration. The sample size of 52 patients (26 each group), though sufficient for initial comparative analyses, limits the generalizability of the findings and the ability to detect subtler differences in outcomes. Future studies would benefit from larger cohorts and multi-centred

designs to better establish these treatments' effectiveness and safety profiles.

Moreover, the follow-up duration of three months, though indicative of short-term outcomes, does not address the longer-term effects of HA or corticosteroid injections. Research, including recent systematic reviews, indicates repeated HA injections maintain efficacy over extended periods. This suggests that a long-term treatment approach could yield even greater benefits and warrants further investigation.²¹

Implications for clinical practice include a more discerning approach to intra-articular injection therapy in knee OA management. Our findings support HA as a primary treatment modality for functional improvement in chronic knee OA, particularly for patients seeking sustainable relief with minimal adverse effects. Conversely, corticosteroids may be judiciously utilized to manage inflammatory episodes rapidly, yet should be employed cautiously, given their potential long-term risks.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that HA injections yield superior functional outcomes compared to corticosteroids at 3 months in knee OA, as evidenced by a greater OKS improvement. However, further research is needed to refine treatment strategies and enhance patient-centred care.

References

Ayhan E, Kesmezacar H, Akgun I. Intraarticular injections (corticosteroid, hyaluronic acid, platelet-rich plasma) for the knee osteoarthritis. *World journal of orthopedics*. 2014 Jul 18;5(3):351. doi: [10.5312/wjo.v5.i3.351](https://doi.org/10.5312/wjo.v5.i3.351)

Evanich JD, Evanich CJ, Wright MB, Rydlewicz JA. Efficacy of intraarticular hyaluronic acid

- injections in knee osteoarthritis. *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research* (1976-2007). 2001 Sep 1;390:173-81. https://journals.lww.com/corr/abstract/2001/09000/efficacy_of_intraarticular_hyaluronic_acid.20.aspx.
- He WW, Kuang MJ, Zhao J, Sun L, Lu B, Wang Y, Ma JX, Ma XL. Efficacy and safety of intraarticular hyaluronic acid and corticosteroid for knee osteoarthritis: a meta-analysis. *International Journal of Surgery*. 2017 Mar 1;39:95-103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijso.2017.01.087>
- Tiwari A, Thora A. Randomized controlled trial comparing the intra-articular Hyaluronic acid versus intra-articular steroid in osteoarthritis of the knee. *International Journal of Research in Orthopaedics*. 2018 Jul;4(4):587-90. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/issn.2455-4510.IntJResOrthop20182020>.
- Geng R, Li J, Yu C, Zhang C, Chen F, Chen J, Ni H, Wang J, Kang K, Wei Z, Xu Y. Knee osteoarthritis: Current status and research progress in treatment. *Experimental and therapeutic medicine*. 2023 Oct 1;26(4):1-1. <https://doi.org/10.3892/etm.2023.12180>.
- Ullah SA, Ahmed F, Sultana N, Hossain SA. Efficacy of combination therapy of Hyaluronic acid and Methylprednisolon verses Hyaluronic acid single therapy in knee Osteoarthritis: A comparative study. *Northern International Medical College Journal*. 2019;10(2):366-9. DOI:10.3329/nimcj.v10i2.45429.
- Tirmizi SH, Fakhr A, Amer A, Yusuf R, Sajjad K, Shah MK. Comparison of the effectiveness of intraarticular injections of hyaluronic acid and corticosteroids in the treatment of patients with knee osteoarthritis symptoms. *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal*. 2021 Aug 31(4):1167. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51253/pafmj.v7i4.4647>
- Askari A, Gholami T, NaghiZadeh MM, Farjam M, Kouhpayeh SA, Shahabfard Z. Hyaluronic acid compared with corticosteroid injections for the treatment of osteoarthritis of the knee: a randomized control trial. *Springerplus*. 2016 Dec;5:1-6. DOI 10.1186/s40064-016-2020-0
- Lin X, Zhi F, Lan Q, Deng W, Hou X, Wan Q. Comparing the efficacy of different intra-articular injections for knee osteoarthritis: A network analysis. *Medicine*. 2022 Aug 5;101(31):e29655. DOI: 10.1097/MD.00000000000029655
- Pramanik R, Basak A, Ballav A. A Comparative Study on Effectiveness of Intra-articular Injection of High Molecular Weight Hyaluronate, Steroid and High Molecular Weight Hyaluronate plus Steroid in Osteoarthritis Knee. *Indian Journal of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*. 2015 Jun 1;26(2):31-7. DOI:[10.5005/jp-journals-10066-0034](https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10066-0034)
- Basak A, Banerjee A. A Comparative Study on Effectiveness of Intra-articular Injection of Steroid and Steroid Plus High Molecular Weight Hyaluronate in Primary Osteoarthritis Knee. *Indian Journal of Physical Medicine & Rehabilitation*. 2018 Oct;29(4):91-6. DOI:[10.5005/jp-journals-10066-0034](https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10066-0034)
- da Costa BR, Hari R, Jüni P. Intra-articular corticosteroids for osteoarthritis of the knee. *Jama*. 2016 Dec 27;316(24):2671-2. <https://boris.unibe.ch/92320/1/daCosta%20JAMA%202016.pdf>.
- Li D, Hang R, Lang M, Zhao Z, Zhao C, Luo F. Co-treatment with oral duloxetine and intraarticular injection of corticosteroid plus hyaluronic acid reduces pain in the treatment of knee osteoarthritis. *Pain Physician*. 2024;27(1):E45. (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-036447>).
- Khongwir W, Saha S, Khonglah T. A comparative study of the results of conservative therapy, intra-articular steroid injection therapy and intra-articular hyaluronic acid injection

- therapy in primary osteoarthritis of knee: a prospective study in Eastern Indian population. *Int J Surg Sci.* 2018;2(3):10-6. DOI: [10.33545/orthor.2018.v2.i3b.59](https://doi.org/10.33545/orthor.2018.v2.i3b.59)
- Mishra AN, Mishra S, Ahmad S. An evaluation of role of intraarticular hyaluronic acid in treatment of osteoarthritis of knee. *International Journal of Orthopaedics.* 2017;3(4):232-5. DOI: [10.22271/ortho.2017.v3.i4d.32](https://doi.org/10.22271/ortho.2017.v3.i4d.32)
- Gosikonda V, Reddy V, Chokkarapu R. Role of viscosupplementation in the management of primary osteoarthritis knee. *International Journal of Research in Orthopaedics.* 2017 Jul;3(4):841. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18203/issn.2455-4510.IntJResOrthop20172884>
- McGrath AF, McGrath AM, Jessop ZM, Gandham S, Datta G, Dawson-Bowling S, Cannon SR. A comparison of intra-articular hyaluronic acid competitors in the treatment of mild to moderate knee osteoarthritis. *J Arthritis.* 2013;2(01):1-5. <https://www.iomcworld.org/open-access/a-comparison-of-intraarticular-hyaluronic-acid-competitors-in-the-treatment-of-mild-to-moderate-knee-osteoarthritis-45821.html>
- Sarkar R, Kumar KV, Nagakumar JS, Kumaar A, SARKAR R, Kumar V. Clinical and Functional Outcomes of Intra-articular Hyaluronic Acid Versus Corticosteroids in Knee Osteoarthritis: A Comparative Study. *Cureus.* 2025 May 23;17(5). DOI: [10.7759/cureus.84712](https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.84712)
- Vaishya R, Pandit R, Agarwal AK, Vijay V. Intra-articular hyaluronic acid is superior to steroids in knee osteoarthritis: A comparative, randomized study. *Journal of Clinical Orthopaedics and Trauma.* 2017 Jan 1;8(1):85-8. doi: [10.1016/j.jcot.2016.09.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcot.2016.09.008)
- Thirunthaiyan MR, Mukherjee K, KR TP. Efficacy of intra-articular corticosteroid and hyaluronic acid injections in preventing progression of early osteoarthritis of the knee in Indian population-A single centre prospective study with a follow-up of 18 months. *International Journal of Orthopaedics.* 2021;7(4):424-30. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22271/ortho.2021.v7.i4.f.2914>
- Buendía-López D, Medina-Quirós M, Fernández-Villacañas Marín MÁ. Clinical and radiographic comparison of a single LP-PRP injection, a single hyaluronic acid injection and daily NSAID administration with a 52-week follow-up: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Orthopaedics and Traumatology.* 2018 Dec;19:1-9. DOI: [10.1186/s10195-018-0501-3](https://doi.org/10.1186/s10195-018-0501-3)